

Analysis of Bash Coffee's Marketing Mix Strategy in Strengthening Coffee Sales in Buraidah

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Introduction

Food and beverage are among the businesses in great demand by business people because apart from being able to generate high profits, food is a basic need of the community. People will need food as the primary source of life wherever and whenever. There has been a shift in the community lifestyle, where they are more open and accustomed to eating outside the home. Apart from being efficient, it can also be used to refresh with family and relatives. This makes business competition in the food and beverage sector more competitive. Likewise, specialty coffee is currently mushrooming and becoming one of the coffee tourism destinations from the downstream industry, which is acculturated with the third wave and has become one of the global trends that is unique to be deepened both from product development to consumer behaviour.

Seeing this opportunity, one of the businesses that has good growth in Buraidah is the restaurant and cafe business, which is one of the gastronomic cities supported by UNESCO, in addition to Saudi Coffee 2022, which is the government's ambition to make the coffee industry sustainable from farm to cup. Furthermore, the market in this region holds much potential and risk, given that there is a lot of growth in the same business sector. This is because the population is large and is supported by a robust economic growth rate. This growth includes the number of outlets and business actors. In this era of increasingly fierce competition, success, creating positive perceptions in the minds of consumers is an essential factor in the success of selling a product; therefore, companies need to convey or communicate a product by touching the emotional side of consumers (Maspul, 2022; Kotler *et al.*, 2018).

With this very tight competition, it is hoped that businesses in each sector or the same industry can move greenly to support each other. This has become commonplace, especially in coffee, in several countries that support each other's business, such as Indonesia and Vietnam.

Even in some not coffee-producing countries, they are solidly supporting each other's progress in specialty coffee. This is due to the solid global association supporting world coffee development at each local level. With the support of the global Specialty Coffee Association (SCA), all members have the latest updates in their respective knowledge, from production to coffee consumption.

Bash Coffee is one of the oldest cafes in Buraidah and has a powerful trust from customers who come back again to enjoy the specialty coffee. With the cafe being the most senior and with the visitors' trust, Bash Coffee started by selling necessities rather than the core sales of the coffee value chain; coffee production. Bash Coffee will begin roasting sales and make it one of the core sales, apart from deals running for the last five years through cold and hot coffee drinks and sweets. Making Bash Coffee sustainable in sales and branding the pride of all stakeholders in Buraidah is a priority desired by all. Likewise, in making Bash Coffee one of the values in the coffee supply chain, making it sustainable in skills and knowledge strengthens the existence of the specialty coffee community in Saudi Arabia.

Problem Statement

Several problems here need to be investigated to find the cause of why Bash Coffee has so far been defeated in coffee sales compared to other visitors who often come to coffee shops in the vicinity.

- The first problem is that Bash has been slow in its development for the last five years, even though it has become a pioneer in developing specialty coffee in the local Buraidah community. It is necessary to understand that an imbalance in the practice of slow-moving business is seeing a tremendous opportunity for developing coffee in Buraidah.

- In addition, the second problem is that the single-origin coffee products are still monotonous and not as varied as other coffeeshops in presenting wide varieties of coffee brought from many producing countries in the world, like Ethiopian and Colombia, which are popular from the local coffee community in Buraidah.
- The third problem is the quality of coffee presentation which is a dilemma for baristas in serving coffee where no standard makes the coffee taste consistent from one fitting to the next for consumers. It is crucial where it is necessary to maintain a constant sense of taste, so there is no consumer dissatisfaction.
- The fourth problem is the inconsistency in handling consumers, where all consumers expect precise handling in presentation. Again, standards are needed to make all services from the barista consistent.
- The fifth problem is the lack of clarity in policies and standards, which is crucial in dealing with consumer complaints and keeping the situation calm in daily operations without making one person the centre of the solution. Still, each barista can be proactive in adequately dealing with day-to-day problems with consumers, even when it's crowded.
- The sixth problem is overstaffing, which is part of the cost of managing this coffee shop. Of course, with appropriate management expenditures, it can succeed in reaping sustainable profits without high staff turnover and increased costs in turning the daily operations of this specialty coffee business.

Cause and Alternatives

1. The Team - Strategically coordinated and timely recruitment, proper training, and skilled management of a dynamic team

According to the latest findings, the following characteristics of a business team heavily affect the survival and growth of a business model within the context of the modern-day industry environment: commitment, ownership, communication, expertise/mastery within the focus area, expertise in business/administration, network/insider contacts, stress coping, coherency (Werther & Chandler, 2010). These factors must be considered and probed during the interview process. The overall team cumulatively and, if possible, individually must score high on as many of these as possible.

The team needs to overcome unexpected barriers with creative troubleshooting and, in case of failures, fail fast and effectively to mould the operations to the market's needs without compromising set values or losing motivation. At the same time, common characteristics that harm management team dynamics should be considered during the interview process and, where possible, avoided or reduced in the overall team score count: third-party needs, vulnerability, and the illusion of control. The last one refers to the mindset of narrow expectations, resulting in poor adaptability and troubleshooting skills (Terwiesch & Xu, 2008).

To engage individuals with the required skill set, it is essential to put together an attractive compensation package that will attract and retain highly skilled team members who are up to the task of building a specialty coffee brand and experience. The team must be allowed adequate time to train and develop meaningful operational practices. Though it may seem costly, this investment will be the most cost-effective long-term solution. In this case, Bash Coffee must review the managerial structure and each job description that must be poured through the central management system in managing its employees.

2. The Vision (Consistent adherence to values and brand vision set as a priority over compromising growth)

In the uncertain start-up phase, clearly defined values and vision are the best tool to navigate the decision-making in the right direction and allow for flexibility/adaptability in a new business environment. This gives the team an anchoring point with which choices and decisions can be assessed, hence, avoiding incoherent operations and internal team conflicts in the early stages of business establishment. In this case, Bash must strengthen branding and how each has the same vision in managing this business to remain sustainable.

3. The Standards (Effective implementation of defined and coherent policies and standards)

A delicate balance must be reached between the flexibility to adapt in the early stages and establishing a firm foundation for the brand's future growth. To achieve that balance, policies and standards must rely upon meaningful operational goals for the team and each team member individually. As the solutions mentioned above to the most common risks are implemented, the competent and motivated staff, driven by defined common values, will be able to build a robust operational structure and policy manual, guided by meaning rather than instructions and micro-management. The need to create an appropriate standard system will make Bash Coffee free from bad management bias, make this business sustainably move well, and continue to make it a pioneer specialty coffee that excels in being the leading sales of specialty coffee (Heisinger & Hoyle, 2012).

Literature Review

1. The Coffee Journey and Specialty Coffee

The coffee journey has a unique history that has long been in-depth known through the *Kaldi* story, furthermore enlivened by the Ottomans in Izmir, Istanbul and Aleppo 350 years ago, which became a bustling place for discussion and a rendezvous for the exchange of ideas between various levels of people with multiple professions (Smith, 1985). Then enlivened in the middle ages, contributed through the Levant's sponsored company and

became a regulated trade with the Ottoman Empire. As the business progresses, coffee shops are places for distinctive sociability. The legacy of coffee that is felt today cannot be separated from the colonialism of coffee slavery in the past through one of the novels by Eduard Douwes Dekker, *Max Havelaar: Or the Coffee Auctions of the Dutch Trade Company*. As of today, coffee's history has always been black but sweet to bring to the sensory area (Ukers, 1935).

Coffee, known only in three types Arabica Robusta and Liberica, has become more diverse. Here, Arabica has many cultivation types and unique branches, which are increasingly varied, even with its progress, providing grades in coffee types, both for Arabica and Robusta. Furthermore, through the development of coffee passed through a long history, it has joined commonly to the term specialty coffee, which has currently become the third wave of the development of coffee itself (Manzo, 2014). The result of coffee shops includes coffee with a mixture of various sweet variants of coffee drinks. But with the vital progress of consumers who want originality and high-quality green coffee taste. So specialty coffee shops have emerged, offering quality coffee concepts with various origins from different countries globally. The coffee shops offer a standard in brewing; after the coffee is roasted, the brew ratio varies in adjusting the taste quality to the limit of post-roasting coffee consumption. Specialty coffee shops will sell coffee for consumption and become a hub for enthusiastic people about the flavours produced by artisan roasting with further sensory on final products' cupping tables. Consumers feel a positive interaction with Baristas through the final products they formulate (Ukers, 1935; Boaventura *et al.*, 2018).

Meanwhile, coffee shops have an exciting atmosphere that makes consumers happy to interact in that place. The design concept is varied in offering the best option to comforting consumers who want to enjoy the espresso quickly or make it an extended spot

to socialise and continue office duties. Apart from being a suitable place to enjoy coffee and sweets, generally in an urban style comfortably, coffee shops have become a place to stop between home and work, making them a third place. Another thing that specialty coffee shops offer is affordable products for consumption rather than enjoying for a long time in a cafe, which requires expensive fees for products and additional services from waiters. Besides, coffee shops for specialty coffee also offer artisan roasted coffee sold as its uniqueness in roasting coffee has added value for a coffee shop. Many coffee shops also sell brewing accessories that consumers can use to brew coffee at home. The brewing accessories vary from manual espresso to various coffee filters (Carvalho & Spencer, 2018).

2. Roasting Skills and Sustainable Knowledge in Coffee Production

It's always interesting when a coffee roaster roasts coffee and turns it into various drinks for customers to order at the coffee shop through the barista. Baristas master additional skills from their performance in understanding coffee production desired by end-users and their expertise in adapting by recognising types and varieties of single origins and standardising management in coffee production spaces. Coffee roasters must understand what consumers want, where each has a variant in asking for the type of coffee roasted. Quality control attracts ideas that turn green coffee into a product end-users want from B2B to B2C. It will build consumer curiosity about single-origin and proper processing and handling in production (Okamura *et al.*, 2021; Xu, 2003).

Sustainability, currently being discussed, has had many positive results in helping general thinking issues. Moreover, sustainability has the best impact on its influence through its three bottom legs: the social economy and the environment. Each has an idea to raise a global issue that the UN has long promoted through the Sustainable Development Goals. Education critically is also one of the outcomes expected to achieve. Likewise,

sustainability cannot be separated from the discussion of coffee in general, the coffee value chain, consumer behaviour, and hospitality. Coffee professionals' need to understand more about coffee is crucial, especially to build resilience in their skills and behaviour. With a sustainable knowledge and sense of both the data and information circulating in the barista environment concerning specialty coffee, The sustainable knowledge will fulfil the coffee professionals' behaviour in environmental terms (WHO, 2019; Haggard *et al.*, 2017)

Despite being the third wave in concept, specialty coffee requires a lot of expertise in coffee roasting and how much knowledge a coffee roaster will gain in deepening their understanding of coffee. It takes consumer satisfaction to get information consistent with what they consume from the coffee products they sell. Apart from selling customers the roasted coffee, they will consume either in their coffee shop or individually, daily training of coffee roasters for quality control calibration in coffee can build confidence. In addition, the consistency of the skill standard of the coffee roaster will provide more value for a constructive personality. Simultaneously, the combination of coffee roaster skills and behaviour will help perfect confidence in their performance in daily coffee production and the management of the coffee roastery itself (Ferreira *et al.*, 2021; Charrier & Eskes, 2004).

Sustainability could be seen in those four contributions in this study from three main activities: production and consumption processes, further following the marketing in the coffee business to encourage coffee business processes to be more sustainable. In the institutional business, sustainability can be verified from the company's efforts, starting by assigning knowledge to the consumers, saving energy consumption, transparent business processes, and decreasing production waste. Furthermore, promoting the company to transform into more sustainable consumer behaviours, keep analysing sustainable values. In practice, coffee professionals must also understand how to think sustainably in science, known as the basis for customer information and sustainable in intelligent behaviour using

the basic needs of coffee roasting and quality control. Understand the prudence in using single-origin when roasting it with care and making coffee as a part of consumers' journey to their needs, respecting farmers for using the harvested coffee beans (Ferreira *et al.*, 2021).

3. Coffee Economics in Saudi Arabia: Connecting Sustainability in Coffee Value Chain

Meanwhile, with the booming growth of coffee in the producing countries following the tropics Cancer and Capricorn, coffee has a strong presence in its demands (de Graaff, 1986). However, with many consumers turning to specialty coffee, some of the challenges are the small number of smallholders who can meet the world's coffee consumption needs in 2030, where predictions from World Coffee Research will be around 25% less (WCR, 2021). Moreover, through the challenges, it is hoped that it will strengthen the economy through policymakers and coffee players from the coffee value chain, helping mitigate challenges and helping the future's demands (Hermans, 2001).

Coffee itself came through colonialism where most countries are related other than the primary producing countries such as Ethiopia and Yemen. Countries that came to coffee through colonialism influences, such as Indonesia, Central America and several other countries in Africa, have become the leading suppliers and are expected to be sustainable with world needs. Several world organisations have tried to help in the sustainability of coffee farmers, but the fact is that it is still far from the farm's needs, especially in New York and London prices as an arbitrage have been set and are considered to be burdensome for coffee farmers. Sustainability in the coffee value chain will not be far from the three bottom legs, stakeholders in making coffee economics sustainable; social, economic, and environmental (Fedkin, 2020; Jeon & Chiang, 1991).

Likewise, China's coffee market has become one of the leading countries in producing coffee, apart from countries influenced by colonialism. China's coffee growth in

its development from 2014 to 2021 reached 27.8% of the average growth rate (Ma, 2022). Moreover, Vietnam's coffee revenue reached \$6.12bn in 2022, with a stock market growing by 4.73% (Statista, 2021). Here Saudi Coffee hopefully could join a progressive role through market data showing that coffee consumption in Saudi Arabia grew by approximately 4% a year between 2016 and 2021 and is forecast to increase by a further 5% per annum up to 2026, reaching an expected annual consumption of 28,700 tons (Godinho, 2022).

Saudi Coffee Company, developed by the Public Investment Fund, is looking for a way out for the sustainability of global coffee. The aim is to position the Kingdom as home to one of the most famous Arabica coffee beans globally, grown in the Jazan region. It is also working to improve the technology used in coffee production locally and provide all the necessary training to enhance the skills of local farmers. With the addition of technological advancements and knowledge of the Kingdom in areas including cultivation, roasting, marketing and sales of coffee and all operations to help position the Kingdom as a leader in the industry (AlHarbi, 2022).

The development of the coffee economy in Saudi Arabia is expected to support and increase sources in the agricultural sector and take advantage of the highlands in Jazan Baha and Aseer, which are also local tourist sites in the Arabian peninsula. Saudi Khawlani's national production of coffee beans includes more than 2,500 coffee plantations with a combined total of about 400,000 coffee trees in the three regions. Meanwhile, the uniqueness of the development of land planted with coffee in the three areas has the region's richness where it enters the Cancer tropics line. The climate and soil requirements are also adequate to grow Arabica with the best quality; in the next ten years, the country's production can increase from 300 tons to 2,500 tons per year. And the company intends to

invest nearly SAR 1.2 billion in the national coffee industry, making 2022 the year of Saudi coffee (Corder, 2022).

The strengthening of this massive coffee project is predicted to support the culture of Saudi as a coffee consumer since ancient times, besides the strengthening of local wisdom that can be acculturated with the trend of the third wave of global coffee. Of course, it is believed that it will strengthen the authentic culture of the existence of coffee as a Saudi identity itself and strengthen the local economy through a sustainable agricultural circle from farm to cup. Apart from that, in maintaining Arab social identity in the region with coffee culture, it is also a unifying source as a cultivating Arab nation apart from nationalism for the people of Saudi Arabia.

Another link with strengthening the local economy is where the coffee community has developed, incorporated through the local coffee community and international organisations such as the Specialty Coffee Association (SCA). Likewise, other international organisations that make coffee quality the best in the scope of global specialty coffee combined with Q grader certification through the Coffee Quality Institute (CQI), which has become a trend in the last five years in Saudi Arabia. The rapid growth of the specialty coffee business through the third-wave generation has become a global culture in providing an additional reference for the term coffee itself without losing the culture of local wisdom coffee in the broader Saudi Arabian community. On the other hand, with the addition of references to the cultural modernisation of consumer behaviour in enjoying coffee, it is believed that it will strengthen a sustainable regional economy. In addition to being a magnet for local sales, it also attracts foreign tourists to enjoy and observe more concerning the global coffee value chain in Saudi Arabia.

Case Study: Bash Coffee

It is necessary to examine more deeply the organisational structure of the management that supported this Bash Coffee Company, approaching by reviewing the problems passed in the previous discussion and finding the right solution. Following the organisational vision and mission of the company, apart from explaining marketing management and strategies that Bash Coffee should use to support the local and broader market (Jensen & Meckling, 2009). It also analyses skillfully opportunity mobility and sustainability, which can be used as a healthy standard in entering the free market through online shopping and the point of sales available at the current main branch (Valentin, 2001). Sustainability is to be achieved by each executive chairholder to represent a positive role in providing daily, monthly and annual reports to the shareholders of this company (Maspul, 2022). Furthermore, it is significant to make an effective organisation at the establishment with appropriate costing so that it can produce many results without burdening the company that we will mention in the final report.

In explaining the core values and market positioning of Bash Coffee through the local and global specialty coffee markets, it is necessary to emphasise its potential. As the consumers are well-versed in the specialty coffee industry, specific core value points and business practices cannot be compromised as they will affect the brand's desirability. Several possible alternatives have been identified, which are discussed below.

Possible Alternatives

1. Bash Coffee brand must establish itself and remain a sustainable specialty coffee value chain from farm to cup.
2. Consistency of taste and quality of the specialty coffee menu items must be a staple of Bash Coffee, which can be reached through skilled sourcing/logical solutions and the establishment of exceptional roasting/brewing standards within the brand.

3. High-quality and fresh specialty coffee roasting must be at the core of Bash Coffee brand's B2C and B2B operations
4. As the art of specialty coffee requires mastery of a skill, the emphasis on experienced, enthusiastic and SCA-certified staff must be a staple of Bash Coffee.

This study will also examine the redefinition of the team and their job specifications to answer the failure of the current policy where there is no clear job description and overstaffing matters. In addition, it is necessary to explain that the diversification of revenue streams without compromising the core values of Bash Coffee will reduce risks in the start-up phase in e-commerce and increase organic growth opportunities. Moreover, it needs to be explained in describing the business plan, which is the goal set in the next five operational years (Spence & Essoussi, 2010).

Bash Coffee's mixed marketing strategy uses the concept of segmenting, targeting, and positioning as follows:

1. Segmenting – Bash Coffee uses geographic and demographic segmentation, grouping its market based on gender, age, place, and type of work.
 - The geographical segmentation of Bash Coffee is based on geography from the Qassim region, one of the big cities, in addition to being one of the UNESCO Creative Cities Network (UCCN) in the field of gastronomy. It has a privilege in this geographical segmentation. Buraidah has also become a pass-by for local travellers who walk from the capital of Saudi Arabia to several cities in the west, which are important cities for the global Islamic society, Mecca and Medina.
 - Demographic Segmentation – Demographically, market segmentation refers to consumers who are grouped into families, organisations or groups, or young people to

adults, with product variants that suit the group, including caffeine and non-caffeine, as well as commercial options and specialty coffee for coffee connoisseurs.

2. Targeting – Bash Coffee's target market is not only students who like coffee activities with a different atmosphere at Qassim University, one of the well-known local campuses. But also, several levels of local society have a strong interest in specialty coffee as one of the third-wave global trends. In addition, the development of specialty coffee is now also increasing, supported by the hectic opening of new coffee shop businesses in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, with the variety of coffee shop themes that currently exist, making coffee shop entrepreneurs have to innovate and have characteristics to win in the competition and target market in this unique industry. It should be understood that coffee shops compete with other coffee shops and restaurants with the same value through their specialty coffee. In addition, because many companies enforce work from home, many consumers choose to work from coffee shops and generally look for outlets that provide heavy food menus, adding to Bash Coffee's target as an environmentally friendly and sustainable place to work for all ages.
3. Positioning – Bash Coffee creates a good impression in its positioning strategy. Bash Coffee has created a positioning in creating a distinctive feature that is different from its competitors. In addition, Bash Coffee has also been nicknamed "Pioneer Specialty Coffee in the region" and "Best Cookies in town" by many people, making it easy for people to remember. A business is said to be successful in its marketing if it survives and thrives among many established coffee shop competitors. It can also determine the right product, brand, place, and carry out the proper promotion. So we need the best plan to make Bash Coffee the best in sales philosophy, including:
 - Product - Bash Coffee is the only coffee shop that carries the theme of simplicity but the best quality specialty coffee, which has its characteristics in the eyes of the public

and its fans because the products contained in Bash Coffee are products that are not commonly sold in other places, such as coffee of the day and cookies together.

- Price - Quality products will be sought after by customers as much as possible to ensure good quality products and provide understanding to consumers. Price is the value of money given to products or services that customers have given to those who offer products or services in return for their satisfaction and desires. The price of a product is the total value of raw materials, semi-finished materials or services and production costs included in the offer. In this case, Bash has become a leader in pressuring coffee and sweet packages in Buraidah. Still, other product developments are needed to cut costs without compromising quality, as explained in the recommendations later.
- Location/place - Determining the right place is one of the most influential things in a business because the more strategic a site is, the more likely it is to bring business success. Kopili is located strategically in the middle of the city of Buraidah and at the Buraidah intersection with 40 coffeeshops and restaurants at the exact location on Othman bin Affan road.
- Promotion - One of the things that are believed to play a role in the stability of sales figures is promotion. Sales promotion is considered a role in introducing new products to consumers. In addition, it also plays a role in brand building by strengthening advertising messages and corporate image. Finally, sales promotions can encourage consumers to make purchases immediately. Bash always tries to excel in promotions by selling the latest coffee products. This is where costing is needed in creating a new strategic plan for the sustainability of product sales from Bash, which will be explained in the next point later.

Recommended Plan Action

While some recommendations from the action plan are as follows:

1. Direct customer sales of specialty coffee menu and pastry items made fresh by Bash's pastry chef.

With the many choices of sweets offered by competitors, Bash Coffee already has a segmentation with many local visitors to take cookies as one of Bash Coffee's biggest markets in providing coffee as a side snack from morning to night. So here it is necessary to re-budget the cost, which for now is still taking it to the supplier, and it is time to hook up the sweet products from Bash Coffee itself. Of course, hiring a chef is still essential to make expenses more sustainable for the economy.

2. Bash's roastery offers B2B beans and pastry sales to local F&B outlets

Similarly, blends and single origins that are used as the core of coffee sales currently still use local coffee roasters, so here it is needed for local production and produce their products. On the other hand, even by marketing sales for B2C and B2B and making the sale of coffee cycles more sustainable than farm to cup, by dealing with farmers from several single origins from several countries in South America and Africa without taking from brokers or traders and can cut from the C price (New York and London). Of course, this requires expertise as an Arabica - Q grader in ensuring that the coffee produced has superior advantages in maintaining the sensory of specialty coffee at a global level. Bash Coffee has three Q graders whose expertise can be maximised in assessing Arabica, making the final product superior in the local market, and even global branding at the core of coffee sales.

3. E-commerce sales (wholesale and individual sales) through a modern web and social media outlet.

E-Commerce is significant because it makes sales wider without limits, especially with the convenience of delivery services for both local and international from DHL to Aramex. In addition, the ease of customs in shipping global goods provides comfort in the

supply chain, both B2C and B2B, especially after the rebranding of Bash coffee through roasting products which are the core of its new production. This advantage will provide extensive input, especially in introducing regional and global new markets.

4. Over the next two years, Bash Coffee will develop its outlets and create opportunities for the global community to build and establish specialty coffee knowledge through the coffee value chain in Bash Coffee.

With the Authorized SCA Trainer - AST (Specialty Coffee Association) based in Bash Coffee, it will be one of the advantages of Bash Coffee to bring new input from the coffee academy. It creates a renewable impact in the coffee market. It strengthens Bash Coffee's position in the Global Coffee Community, as well as sustainability reports that will be carried out to increase knowledge in the world coffee market from all segments and elements. Likewise, the current AST has six complete modules of the Coffee Skills Program and the Coffee Sustainability Program, making it different from the general coffee market, which only sells coffee. The importance here is to develop local expertise and maintain specialty coffee knowledge in the global coffee community.

5. Coffee Subscription: In addition to selling roasted coffee beans (250gr and 1kg size) for individuals through retail and wholesale, Bash Coffee can make weekly/monthly subscriptions for consumer needs used by the subscription package delivered fresh to their doorstep.

In addition to adding channels from points of sales in the form of a coffee academy and sales of roasted coffee itself, here it can add a subscription for selling coffee in large quantities, both for kilo and 250gr, which can be sold in large quantities, both weekly and monthly. This will add marketing from the point of sales and maintain the freshness of the coffee itself so that it will always be unique and consumption is not more than a month from the roasting date. It is essential to know that freshness is one of the most critical keys

than specialty coffee itself, so the community will always make Bash Coffee the standard in the region in maintaining consistency in production and specialty coffee itself.

6. Coffee Hub and Event Hosting: Besides providing intensive courses through the Specialty Coffee Association program, Bash Coffee can give regional hub and global coffee events. In addition to strengthening branding, it will offer a strong diversification in understanding local and international consumers.

Specialty coffee makes consumers a strong community whose knowledge can constantly be updated. Coffee hosting and introducing specialty coffee to the regional and global community here requires a driving force from the coffee community. In this case, Bash Coffee, as the home of the global AST (Authorised SCA Trainer) in the region, is needed in addition to the form of the marketing mix to introduce local and international communities to their knowledge of specialty coffee but also making Bash Coffee a professional coffee player in strengthening the market. By holding a regional or global coffee event with competitions or cupping sessions to introduce Bash's newest roasting product, Bash Coffee will make Bash Coffee unique in the hectic global trend of specialty coffee.

7. Bash Coffee can offer franchise opportunities to retailers worldwide by rebranding a solid brand and operations.

Taking advantage of the momentum in the specialty coffee trend in the world can make Bash a key in the existence of a sustainable brand, joining forces with renewable brands such as Japanese % Arabica but emphasising specialty coffee that is more consistent with the standards of product quality.

In addition, it is necessary to rethink the effectiveness of Bash Coffee's organisational structure so that it does not spend much on its management and operations. This is precisely by explaining their respective job descriptions in their roles at Bash Coffee. As for facilitating

the course of communication in the success of this business operation journey, it is necessary to explain related to the divisional staffing structure in Bash Coffee as below:

Fig 1. Hierarchical Bash Coffee Operations

1. Executive Head of Coffee

It is important to note here that: The Executive Head of Coffee, during the early stages of production of Bash Coffee, had full responsibility for the core of the coffee value chain from procurement to production and sales. Executive Head of Coffee will manage Bash Coffee's overall operations. This may include delegating and directing agendas, driving profitability, managing company organisational structure and strategy, and communicating with the Board of Directors. In addition, it also has responsibilities as follows:

- Overseeing the day-to-day operations of the coffee HQ production and coffee shops
- Solving challenges faced by customers and employees
- Overseeing cleanliness and maintenance of the shop

- Hiring and training employees
- Adjusting menu to maintain customer flow

2. Head of Finance

This position is needed to assist the operations in bookkeeping, record all Bash Coffee data from employment to sales and profit, and coordinate with the Executive Head of Coffee, the production department, and the head barista. Some of his responsibilities include the following:

- Handling cash flow, financial planning, and legal and taxation issues.
- Providing administrative support to the day-to-day management of OT's financial accounting and payroll processes.
- Administration of all income and receipts processes, ensuring completeness of income against invoices issued and grant payments due.
- Bookkeeping, maintaining records, and running deposits.

3. Head of Coffee Roasters

Coffee Roasters have an essential role in the production and sale of essentially B2B within Bash Coffee. The coffee roaster, also the Production Manager, requires skills and chemistry of output and communicating with businesses that take production from Bash Coffee, both from hotel lounges and coffee shops in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. In other cases, communication requires the coffee roaster to intensively coordinate with the barista for sensory skills evaluation and the HR Finance Manager for procurement and daily monthly reporting of B2B sales. Some of the basic skills that Coffee Roaster (Production Manager) possess are as follows:

- Receiving green coffee deliveries, staging Green Coffee for daily roasts
- Weighing green coffee in preparation for roasting

- Contribute to Quality Control - through cupping and other brew methods
- Blending roasted coffee in preparation for packing
- Packing roasted coffee
- Record keeping and data entry
- General roastery cleaning and maintenance of roasting equipment
- Participate in a cupping of production roasts and new offerings
- Work closely with Coffee Program Manager on developing new offerings and roast profiles
- Following Strict Sanitation Practices, Maintaining and Cleaning all necessary roasting equipment
- Learning and maintaining roast profiles for a variety of brewing platforms

4. Head of Baristas

Baristas are the leading players in producing coffee in the coffee value chain's downstream area and have an essential role in the sales growth of B2C of Bash Coffee. Barista has a position under the Sales Manager, who is also the head barista, in one team. In this case, the Head Barista collects reporting data from daily and monthly sales and communicates with HR Finance for procurement and the Head of Coffee for all approvals. Some of the basic skills possessed by Head Baristas and Baristas include:

- Specialty coffee brewing skills
- Cashiering duties
- Maintaining inventory, ordering, and receiving products
- To perform ad hoc runner/barback/host duties when required
- Daily operations
- Proper maintenance and care for all coffee equipment – includes thorough daily cleaning after peak hours, as well as maintaining a clean work area throughout the day

- Recommended food items like main courses, sandwiches and bread to go along with the coffee or tea
- Good understanding of the various types of coffee range
- Ordering and managing inventory
- Beverage creation/preparation
- Organising internal and external events
- Supervisory and people skills

5. e-Commerce Manager

e-Commerce has an essential role in online sales, both for individuals and wholesalers. Its function is needed able to strengthen downstream coffee sales through web-based services. Collaborate with other staff in promoting coffee both online and offline. Some of the roles that are the primary responsibilities include:

- Driving the sales performance of the coffee e-commerce platform
- Managing and executing coffee promotional campaigns
- Providing coffee insights on customer shopping trends to support assortment selection and identify assortment gaps
- Ensuring excellent customer service by addressing and ensuring the timely resolution of customer issues or comments
- Working closely with demand coffee planning and warehousing teams to ensure smooth order fulfilment.
- Providing coffee analysis and reporting on metrics such as weekly/monthly sales by department, new coffee products (coffee consumption and accessories), sell-through and offer code performance.

Conclusion

In explaining the massive development of specialty coffee in Saudi Arabia, especially in Buraidah, it has mushroomed, making many coffee entrepreneurs develop new business skills to revitalise this industry. As a pioneer of specialty coffee, Bash Coffee should implement good management to remain sustainable in the social economy and environment, including the implementation of exemplary policy standards and further significantly can implement a marketing strategy that can support the sustainability of its sales structure and open other sales channels such as online. Lastly, by increasing core sales with roasted coffee production, Bash can showcase its role in the B2B and B2C value chain. Of course, with the application of management in a good organisation, Bash Coffee will also be able to strengthen the personnel involved in this business, directly from staff and shareholders from board members to consumers.

Understanding analysis through costing and profitability are critical because no business can operate at a loss; The rather complex problems that Bash Coffee has unwittingly faced over the last five years are crucial but fundamental ones that arise in a disorganised and not well-structured business environment. Therefore, this case study allows those who benefit from understanding the importance of organisational human resources, program and operational management, accounting, leadership and professional recommendations, especially in business operations, policymaking and decision making; all incorporated cycles must synergise in an appropriate and sustainable strategic frame. In concluding the study, it is necessary to emphasise the analysis of Bash Coffee's marketing mix strategy in strengthening coffee sales in Buraidah. It will be done by deepening the study of the specialty coffee market, core values and market positioning, potential revenue streams, risk analysis and solutions through actual problems and, of course, with structured goals for the next five years that will make Bash Coffee much more resilient with an appropriate strategic plan.

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Appendix I

Rubric for Unit 3 Paper

Section One – Problem Statement:

1. Provide an introduction to the case study selected for the final assignment due in Week 8.
2. Provide a detailed background of the subject-company or enterprise.
3. Provide a description of the problem situation in which the subject company or enterprise finds itself.
4. Provide sufficient detail of the subject and its situation to provide the basis for identifying the problem it faces.

Section Two – Statement of Cause(s):

5. Provide analysis of what the root cause of the company/enterprise's problem
6. Provide sufficient descriptive detail to provide adequate information for a subsequent discussion of proposed solutions/recommendations.

Grading Criteria

Provided an introduction to the case study selected for the final assignment due in Week 8	10-points	10
Provide a detailed background of the subject-company or enterprise	20-points	20
Provide a description of the problem situation in which the subject company or enterprise finds itself	10-points	10
Provide sufficient detail of the subject and its situation to provide the basis for identifying the problem it faces	20-points	15
Provide analysis of what the root cause of the company/enterprise's problem. The paper: (A) Provided sufficient descriptive detail to provide adequate information for a subsequent discussion of proposed solutions/recommendations; and (B) Supported its observations with research and logic.	30-points	25
Overall Mechanics/Professionalism: Paper is well organized, contains no writing and spelling errors, and is fully consistent with graduate-level writing style as expected and required for the assignment.	5 points	1
APA Style and Format: Follows the APA style (i.e., scholarly tone, paraphrasing, citations, sources, reference and title pages, line-spacing, section/paragraph headings, indentations, and alignment of tables and figures) accurately and consistently throughout the paper.	5 points	1
TOTAL	100-points	82

Appendix II

Rubric for Unit 6 Paper

Superior written essays will mention and explain the following elements when responding to the assignment question:

Section One – Possible Alternatives: Provide a narrative that comprehensively explores the possible solutions to the problem identified in the student’s Week 3 written assignment by:

1. Briefly restate the problem statement and cause(s) of the problem discussed in Week 3’s written assignment.
2. Provide a narrative that states alternative solutions to the problem and logically connects the problem/cause to the alternatives being suggested.

Section Two – Recommended Plan of Action:

3. Provide an analysis and evaluation of each alternative and;
4. Provide a final recommendation.
5. Provide a high level implementation plan stating what steps should be taken

Grading Criteria

Provided a restatement of the problem and cause(s) discussed in Week 3’s written assignment.	10-points	10
Provided a narrative that states alternative solutions to the problem and logically connects the problem/cause to the alternatives being suggested.	25-points	25
Provide an analysis and evaluation of each alternative.	25-points	25
Provided a final recommendation.	15-points	12
Provided a high level implementation plan stating what steps should be taken.	15-points	12
Overall Mechanics/Professionalism: Paper is well organized, contains no writing and spelling errors, and is fully consistent with graduate-level writing style as expected and required for the assignment.	5 points	2
APA Style and Format: Follows the APA style (i.e., scholarly tone, paraphrasing, citations, sources, reference and title pages, line-spacing, section/paragraph headings, indentations, and alignment of tables and figures) accurately and consistently throughout the paper.	5 points	2
TOTAL	100-points	88

Appendix III

Rubric for Presentation**Grading Criteria**

Introduced the company, provided relevant background, and provided a clear explanation of the problem and its cause(s).	20-points	20
Suggested alternative solutions to address the problem and logically connected the problem/cause to the alternatives being suggested.	15-points	15
Discussed his/her analysis and evaluation of each alternative.	15-points	15
Provided a final recommendation.	15-points	15
Described what steps should be taken to implement recommendations.	15-points	15
Presentation was well organized and flowed logically.	10- points	10
Demonstrated competency in their topic and answered follow-up questions.	10- points	10
TOTAL	100-points	100

Arif,

It was a pleasure speaking with you today. Your knowledge about specialty coffee, the industry, and Bash in particular is very impressive. It is clear that you understand Bash from the bottom-up and top-down, which speaks to the depth and breadth of your knowledge.

You've done an excellent job describing the problems you see in the current business model, possible alternatives, and a potential plan of action. You also did a great job fielding questions, which is a testament to your ability to think on your feet. Today's session was upbeat and informative. It was rewarding to me as an instructor, to see how well you are able to apply your learnings from your studies.

The strengths of your presentation:

- Knowledge of the topic
- Strong critical thinking and problem-solving skills
- An ability to think on your feet
- One of my favorite parts of our conversation was to hear about the open-mindedness of your Saudi colleagues for your ideas about Bash as well as to learn that they are also graduates of UoPeople. This makes me feel very proud of you and the university.

Weaknesses:

The only improvement I would suggest is to slow down when you are presenting. Relax! Breathe! Smile! I know that speaking to your instructor about your work (and public speaking in general) can be a bit nerve-racking; **but you did great!** Keep in mind, you are the expert. You were educating/informing me about your project. Let your confidence shine through. You've got this.

In closing, let me reiterate that I enjoyed your presentation very much, and especially your passion, commitment, and enthusiasm, which comes across very naturally. There's a saying, "Love what you do, do what you love." This could very well be your mantra.

If you have any questions or concerns about the course or the final paper, please do not hesitate to ask.

Kind regards and congratulations on a job well done,

Dr. B.